

Comparative Study of Proverbs Expressing Diligence in English and Uzbek

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ABSTRACT

The study of English proverbs contributes not only to the enrichment of vocabulary, but also to acquaintance with the cultural and national identity of the people, as well as with the mentality and national character of its representatives.

The purpose of the article is to analyze from the point of view of semantics, structure and phraseological image the conceptual series of English proverbs in comparison with Uzbek proverbs associated with the concept of "labor", that is, reflecting the similarities and differences in the attitude towards labor of the British and Uzbek people. It is the attitude to "labor", "work" that has always occupied an important place in the life of people. A respectful attitude to work, a negative attitude to laziness, and an inactive way of life is embedded in the proverbs of both the Uzbek and English languages.

Keywords: Phraseology, labor, proverbs, national identity, comparison, phraseological units.

INTRODUCTION

Phraseology occupies a significant place in the lexical fund of any language as part of the national and cultural heritage of the people.

We chose proverbs as the subject of our analysis, that is, such phraseological units that, in their structural and grammatical design, are complete sentences containing teachings, edifications, but in addition expressing a rich range of connotative comprehension (evaluation, expression, emotionality, etc.). In

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addition, they differ in both rhythmic-intonation and phonetic design (parallelism of construction, poetic meter, sound repetitions, rhymes, etc.) [2].

One of the factors that express the national values and culture of the nation, which show the identity of the nation, is the oral creativity of the people. Proverbs, one of the most important genres of folklore, are one of the most important topics studied in linguistics and folklore. The study and research of proverbs, which are one of the most important genres of folklore, and folk art in general, is of great importance today. We will also bring up the aspects of the study of Uzbek and English folk proverbs in linguistics and get acquainted with the theories of scientists who worked in this field. Folk proverbs, which arose as a unique phenomenon of language, philosophy and artistic creation, are a genre of folklore with a compact form, but deep content. Each of these artistic drops, which can show the beauty of our language, the elegance of our speech, the intelligence and logic of our thinking with amazing power, are a wonderful mirror of our people's centuries-old life experiences and everyday life. His attitude to life, nature, man, family and society, socio-political, spiritual-educational, moral-aesthetic and philosophical views, in short, his Self and Identity are fully manifested in this artistic mirror. [3] For this reason, proverbs are very common and have been used for centuries not only in everyday speech and conversation, but also in artistic, historical and scientific works, political and journalistic literature, and are still very popular today.

DISCUSSIONS

Proverbs are a widespread independent genre of oral artistic creativity as rare examples of folk wisdom. Conditionally, they can be called the rules of public etiquette. After all, proverbs are a phenomenon born from the very concise, concise, dense and figurative expression of the socio-political, spiritual-cultural,

moral-philosophical views of the people tested in their life experiences over the centuries. Proverbs are not specially created, but arise as a judgment as a moral assessment of the conclusion born from life experience tested due to the requirements of certain conditions. They show that in the process of people's activities in various fields, they are the product of long-term life experiences, stable and unchanging, correct and truthful conclusions. Folk art has its own laws and principles of development. These features are studied by the field of paremiology of folklore studies. As we conduct research on proverbs, we must turn to the field of paremiology.

Paremia is a Greek word that means wisdom, proverb, wise saying. Paremiography deals with the collection, recording and reading of examples of folk art. In folklore, the genre of proverbs is a part of folk creativity, as it is directed to wisdom, is very concise, concise and figurative. However, the genre of the proverb is not recognized as a separate literary genre until today, and it is seen as a sub-genre, sometimes abstractly, in the composition of folk prose and folk poetry. A proverb is one of the genres of oral creativity with a concise and deep meaning, which was created on the basis of the experiences and observations accumulated by the people in the socio-economic, political and cultural life over many centuries. The term proverb is derived from the Arabic word - qawlun - to speak, to say, and is used for spoken expressions and phrases.

Phrases and expressions that are said almost identically by everyone and are understood in the same way make up the genre of proverbs. [1] So, folk proverbs consist of expressions and expressions with a unique artistic form that perfectly embody the conclusions, judgments and recommendations of the public about specific events and events. Uzbek folk proverbs are often proverbs, sayings of

wisdom, words of wisdom, sayings of elders, sayings of mentors, sayings of poets and sayings of fathers.

The term proverb is often used in scientific context. Proverbs are an international genre by their nature. There is no nation in the world that does not have its own proverbs. Because, every nation leaves its life experiences to generations in the form of proverbs. That is why there are many proverbs that are close to each other in terms of content and form in the oral works of different nations. Because there are many similarities in the life and history of each nation [1].

The English language has a thousand-year history. During this time, it has accumulated a large number of expressions that people found successful, accurate and beautiful. And so a special layer of the language arose - phraseology, a set of stable expressions that have an independent meaning.

For those who study English as a foreign language, this layer of the language is difficult to master, but after mastering phraseological units, you begin to speak like Englishmen, you understand them from a half-word, your speech readiness increases dramatically. You can briefly and very accurately express your thought, being sure of the correctness of its expression.

Proverbs and sayings are the pearls of folk art, which reflect the experience, faceted for centuries and passed from mouth to mouth, from generation to generation. It is precisely because of their brightness, imagery and emotionality that proverbs and sayings are often found in various types of texts in English. However, when translating proverbs and sayings contained in English texts into Uzbek, there are often difficulties, since their meaning may not always be clear to us, and their interpretation is not always given in English-Uzbek and Uzbek-English dictionaries.

On the one hand, it should be noted that many English and Uzbek proverbs and sayings have multiple meanings, which makes them difficult to interpret and compare. Formed in different historical conditions, English and Uzbek sayings and proverbs often used different images to express the same or similar thoughts, which, in turn, reflect the different social structure and life of the two peoples and often are not absolute equivalents. It should be noted that in every language there are phrases and expressions that cannot be taken literally, even if the meaning of each word is known and the grammatical construction is clear. The meaning of this phrase remains incomprehensible and strange. Attempts to literally translate proverbs and sayings can lead to unexpected, often ridiculous results.

In this part of our scientific work, analyzing the linguistic and cultural characteristics of some proverbs in the English and Uzbek languages, we will show the expression of the unique national character of both peoples, their daily lifestyle. Basically, by critically analyzing the proverbs of both languages, we will study their differences and try to express the common aspects of their similarities using the necessary sources. Proverbs are a priceless example of folk creativity, they express the national-cultural characteristics, worldview and spirit of the nation. As the famous linguist Dal said, "a collection of proverbs is a set of wisdoms from the language of the people, from experience, common sense, the truth that people have acquired in life." [2] If we dwell on the proverbs of different languages, we will witness that they are a reflection of the historical, spiritual and material culture of the people who own that language. Therefore, the comparative study of proverbs of different languages helps to reveal the specific cultural and national aspects of a nation, in other words, it shows the mentality of that nation. Although the concept of "mentality" has not yet been included in the paradigm of linguistics, it is currently used in a very wide range. In a narrow sense, mentality is used in the

context of "frame of thinking, worldview", and in a broad sense, "ethics, education and imagination of the people are understood" [10]

1. *Speak less but do more.*

- *Ko'p gapirma, ko'p ishla. Qo'ling ishda, ko'ngling Allohda bo'lsin.*

2. *The workman is known by his work.*

- *Usta ishi bilan mashhur. Usta, ishni qilar yuzta.*

3. *The labourer is worthy of his hire.*

- *Ishlagan ish haqiga loyiqdir.*

- *Ishlab topganing –osh,*

Ishlamay topganing- tosh.

As we can see, the existence of proverbs about work and diligence in Uzbek and English languages shows that both peoples are very hardworking and hardworking. Therefore, all the proverbs that we have mentioned are among the topics that are widely used in people's lifestyles. At this point, even if we talk about their semantic scope, we understand that the meaning of proverbs is exactly the same. For example, when translating the proverb "A man of words and not of deeds is like a garden full of weeds" into Uzbek, it means "*Ishlamasdan so'zlovchi odam o't bosgan bog'ga o'xshar.*" Through this proverb, we describe people who do not like work, but are very talkative. But we cannot always use the Uzbek translation or meaning of an English proverb ready for the Uzbek language. Significantly, the proverb is still very active among both peoples today. We can use it not only in our daily life, but we can also see its beautiful presence in artistic works. As a very beautiful and alternative version of this, we can cite "*Ish bilsang tuzarsan, bilmasang buzarsan.*" In the Uzbek language, we can use the proverb "*Ish ishtaha ochar, dangasa ishdan qochar*" as an equivalent to this proverb.

As another proof of our opinion, let's consider the English proverb "Head cook and bottle-washer". The translation of the proverb in Uzbek is "*Ham bosh oshpaz, ham tovoq yuvuvchi*". The meaning of the proverb is that a person is engaged in several jobs, or is the owner of several professions at the same time. At first glance, the proverb has educational value and shows aspects encouraging working. As we have already mentioned, proverbs are a product of folk oral creativity and are the result of people's assessment of their life experience and aspirations, and their attitude towards life in general. A large number of proverbs on the topic of hard work in English and Uzbek languages complement each other semantically. In the proverbs on the topic of hard work in both languages, encouraging a person to be hardworking.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, in English and Uzbek proverbs, all national traditions from the past to the present day are reflected, and as rare examples of folk creativity, proverbs take the lead in fulfilling this task. When studying the semantic characteristics of the Uzbek and English people, Uzbek and English proverbs can show the similarities and differences between these two peoples. Proverbs are of great importance for every nation. According to proverbs, every nation takes an example for itself, an example of wisdom. As a result, when translating proverbs and sayings contained in English texts into Uzbek, there are often difficulties, since their meaning may not always be clear to us. On the one hand, it should be noted that many English and Uzbek proverbs and sayings have multiple meanings, which makes them difficult to interpret and compare. It should be noted that in every language there are phrases and expressions that cannot be taken literally, even if the meaning of each word is known.

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